

A Phonetically and Prosodically Annotated Slovene Speech Corpus

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Abstract

The domain of spoken language technologies ranges from speech input and output systems to complex understanding and generation systems, including multi-modal systems of widely differing complexity (such as automatic dictation machines) and multilingual systems (for example automatic dialogue and translation systems). The definition of standards and evaluation methodologies for such systems involves the specification and development of highly specific spoken language corpus and lexicon resources, and measurement and evaluation tools (EAGLES Handbook 1997). This paper presents the MobiLuz spoken resources of the Slovene language, which will be made freely available for research purposes in speech technology and linguistics.

1. Introduction

The domain of spoken language technologies ranges from speech input and output systems to complex understanding and generation systems, including multi-modal systems of widely differing complexity (such as automatic dictation machines) and multilingual systems (for example automatic dialogue and translation systems).

The definition of standards and evaluation methodologies for such systems involves the specification and development of highly specific spoken language corpus and lexicon resources, and measurement and evaluation tools.

In the beginning, standards for these areas have been derived from the consensus within the spoken language community previously established in a number of European and national projects, with reference to important initiatives in the US and Japan.

Primary among these have been the SAM projects (centered on component technology assessment and corpus creation), SQALE (for large vocabulary systems assessment) and both SUNDIAL and SUNSTAR (for multi-modal systems.)

Past and present projects with significant outputs in the domain of assessment and resources include ARS, RELATOR, ONOMASTICA and SPEECHDAT, as well as major national projects and programs of research such as VERBMOBIL in Germany.

This has led to an initial documentation of existing practice which was relatively comprehensive but in many respects heterogeneous and widely dispersed.

The lack of generic technologies and resources and the wide diversity of formats and specifications has hindered the effective reutilisation of existing resources.

In 1993, the EAGLES (Expert Advisory Group on Language Engineering Standards) initiative was launched within the framework of the CEU's DGXIII Linguistic Research and Engineering (LRE) Programme, to accelerate the provision of standards for developing, exploiting and evaluating large-scale language resources.

A special working group has been set up for this purpose, named the Spoken Language Working Group (SLWG). The project resulted in the publication of comprehensive guidelines documenting existing working practices in Europe and guidelines for spoken language resource creation and description (EAGLES Handbook 1997).

2. Slovene Speech Corpora

For the Slovene language, several attempts in speech data collection were made in the past, resulting in various speech corpora:

- ❖ SNABI (Kačič, 1994; Kačič, 1998),
- ❖ LUZ diphones (Gros, 1996),
- ❖ GOPOLIS (Dobrišek, 1998) and
- ❖ SPEECHDAT-Slovene (Kaiser, 1998), distributed by ELRA.

The collected speech data mainly represented the domain of intended applications and are not available for distribution, except for the Slovenian SpeechDat(II) FDB-1000 corpus containing phonetically rich sentences. The corpus consists of read and spontaneous speech and was recorded through an ISDN card (1.000 speakers). A phonetic lexicon with canonical transcriptions in SAMPA is also provided.

However, due to its high cost (20.000 EUR) the Slovene SPEECHDAT corpus can hardly be used for research or even development purposes. We therefore decided to create a collection of various Slovene speech data, freely available for research purposes in speech technology and linguistics. Such speech resources are essential for building multi-lingual speech recognition and text-to-speech synthesis applications.

The idea is in the process of being realized within the MobiLuz project funded by the Slovene Ministry of Science and Technology and the Slovene mobile telephony operator Mobitel d.d.

The MobiLuz project collects and integrates resources of several previous project, e.g. the EU Copernicus SQEL and MULTEXT-East and will provides three main deliverables:

1. MobiLuz Slovene speech corpus,
2. MobiLuz Slovene speech corpus annotations and lexicon and
3. MobiLuz speech tools.

The next three sections detail our work on these deliverables.

3. MobiLuz Slovene speech corpus

The MobiLuz Slovene speech corpus includes various collections of speech data pronounced by multiple speakers, either as read speech or spontaneous speech. In particular, the corpus consists of the following components:

- a fully updated and revised version of the 50 speaker GOPOLIS corpus of air travel inquiries,
- recordings of live dialogs.

3.1. Gopolis

The GOPOLIS corpus is a large multi-speaker speech database, derived from real situation dialogs concerning airline timetable information services. It was used as the Slovenian speech database within the SQEL project (Copernicus COP-94 contract No. 01634) for building a multi-lingual speech recognition and understanding dialog system (Ipšič et al. 1997), capable of passing information over the telephone line to a client in one of four European languages - German, Czech, Slovak and Slovenian.

The name of the database has been derived from "GOvorjena POizvedovanja o Letalskih Informacijah v Slovenskem jeziku", meaning "Spoken Flight Information Queries in the Slovene Language".

The sentence corpus was drawn from listening to recordings of real situation dialogs between anonymous clients' inquiries and telephone operators at the Adria Airways information center (15 hrs of speech stored on audiotapes).

The selected 300 typical sentences were compiled into the form of rewrite rules to obtain a generative sentence pattern grammar (Gros et al., 1995). Using this grammar, we produced 22,500 different sentences for short introductory inquiries, long inquiries and short confirmations. 5,077 of them were selected to form the final sentence corpus.

Each of the total of 50 speakers (25 female and 25 male) read about 100 randomly selected unique corpus sentences and 71 sentences of welcome greetings, introductory phrases, short affirmations and farewell greetings, common to all of the speakers. Each session has a list of attributes with speaker and recording session descriptors.

3.2. Recording conditions

The recording sessions were performed in a normal laboratory acoustic environment. Additional noise, such as background speech or slamming doors was avoided.

The utterances were acquired by a close talking microphone and simultaneously by telephone. Thus an additional analysis of both audio devices was enabled.

A set of recording environment programs was developed for the HP 9000 workstation platform. The user interface program built for recording communicates with two audio servers over the network, displays and saves the acquired signals and displays the sentences that a speaker should utter (Figure 1). So the acoustic realizations are in form of read continuous speech.

The program is also equipped with loudness detection and an acoustic messaging system. It takes care of the correct maximum loudness level, begin and end pauses and synchronizes the acquired telephone and microphone speech signals.

The audio servers use the HP 9000/735 common audio hardware components and the additional Gradient Technology DeskLab hardware with a full telephone interface (DeskLab is a data acquisition and play device, which communicates via SCSI with a workstation).

The speaker has to press a space bar key to signal the start of the recording session and then again to finish it. The program requires at least half a second of silence at the beginning and at the end of the utterance.

A sampling rate of 16 kHz for both microphone and telephone signals and a 16-bit data format with MSB-LSB byte order was chosen.

4. Corpus annotations and lexica

The GOPOLIS corpus is encoded in accordance with TEI recommendations (Sperberg-McQueen and Burnard, 1994), in particular, the base tagset for Transcriptions of Speech, the additional tagsets for Simple Analytic Mechanisms and Language Corpora, and some local modifications. The corpus contains the TEI header, giving the File, Encoding and Profile descriptions. The body of the corpus consists of the 5,077 sentences (utterances), each marked with an ID and references to its speakers.

The utterances are segmented into words (41,244) and punctuation marks (5,856), and each word has been automatically tagged for its lemma and morphosyntactic

description. Furthermore, the data also contains prosodic annotations. To illustrate, we give on the right the encoding of one utterance:

```
<u id="gp.0008">
  <w lemma="dober" msd="Afpmsnn">Dober</w>
  <w lemma="dan" msd="Ncmsn">dan</w>
  <event desc="B1">
  <w lemma="železi" msd="Voip1s--n">želim</w>
  <c>!</c>
</u>
```


Figure 1: Recording Session Setup

Two lexica accompany the corpus: a pronunciation dictionary and a word-form lexicon with the morphosyntactic descriptions.

4.1. Transcription and tagging

The phonetic transcriptions in the corpus are based on the Slovene MRPA set (Dobrišek, 1996; Zemljak, 2000) containing machine-readable phonetic symbols equivalent to the Slovene IPA symbols (Šuštaršič, 1998).

The morphosyntactic descriptions and lexicon are based on the MULTEXT-East (Slovene) tagset and lexicon (Dmitrova et al., 1998; Ide et al., 1998). The lexicon contains lemmas, their full inflectional paradigms and the morphosyntactic descriptions of the wordforms (Erjavec, 1998). The descriptions have a feature-structure like format and encode informations such as part-of-speech, number, case, etc. So, in the example above, the morphosyntactic description *Afpmsnn* stands for Adjective qualificative positive masculine singular nominative non-definitene. These descriptions and lexicon were then used to automatically tag and lemmatise the corpus. The tool used for tagging was the trigram tagger TnT (Brants, 2000), which had been trained on the Slovene MULTEXT-East corpus.

4.2. Speech segmentation and alignment

The automatic segmentation is performed using the DTW based approach described in (Dobrišek, 1997) where the speech material is automatically segmented and labelled using dynamic time warping alignment of a natural utterance with a synthesised speech signal.

The synthesis of speech signals was achieved by simply concatenating labelled diphone speech signals using a simplified TD-PSOLA technique. The diphone inventory used was borrowed from the Slovenian text-to-

speech system *S5* (Gros, 1997). The diphone inventory consists of a set of segmented and labelled diphone speech signals. Every diphone in the inventory is segmented into two separated phones and voiced phones were additionally marked with pitch period markers.

According to the phonetic transcription of the natural speech signal, a sequence of concatenated diphone speech signals was generated. A conventional DTW alignment of the utterance with the synthesised speech signal was performed with two sequences of feature vectors derived from both speech signals. This method has the advantage that we do not need labelled reference speech signals since we know the phone boundaries of the synthetic speech signal.

5. Speech Tools

The MobiLuz speech corpus will be accompanied by the Sigmark software developed in cooperation with Masterpoint, a user-friendly program interface which allows manual editing, viewing and marker corrections of speech signals on various levels (phone, word and phrase levels).

Markers can also be copied from one level to the other which proves to be very useful for synchronising marker sets on different levels.

6. Conclusion

The MobiLuz project is aiming to set up an infrastructure of Slovene spoken resources necessary for building various multi-lingual speech recognition and synthesis applications. For example, the GOPOLIS speech corpus, which will become available in the scope of MobiLuz, has already been successfully used for training of the HMM-based speech recognition engine in the multilingual automatic dialog system SQEL (Ipšič, 1998).

7. Acknowledgements

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